

ACADEMIC INTEREST AS A CORRELATE OF ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NNEWI EDUCATION ZONE, ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA.

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<p>Keywords: Academic interest, Academic Achievement, English Language and Public Secondary Schools.</p>	<p>Abstract: <i>Willingness and curiosity towards learning can stimulate academic interest among students. This study examined academic interest as correlates of academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. The study was guided by three research questions and one hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 8,150 SS2 students in the 48 public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. Multi-stage random sampling procedure was used to draw a sample size of 782 students. The instruments for data collection were Students' Academic Interest Questionnaire (SAIQ) and SS2 Students Achievements Scores (SAS) in English Language. The instruments were validated by experts and the consistency established using Cronbach alpha reliability index, which yielded an aggregate of 0.81 coefficient and was considered fit for the study. The administration of the instruments were done through the direct method approach with the help of four research assistants. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was utilized for data analysis. The p-value was used to determine the relationship of the variables at 0.05 level of significance for the hypothesis. The findings of the study revealed that academic interest has a high positive and significant relationship on academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. The study recommended among others that Anambra State government in collaboration with the principals in Nnewi Education Zone should organize seminars, workshops or conferences to enlighten the students on the need to develop academic interest towards learning of school subjects especially the English Language.</i></p>
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Introduction

Priorities on increased quality of instruction, improved standard of education and excellence in academics remain crucial factors for achievement of educational goals and enhanced functional education system. Primary efforts of teachers, school counsellors, school administrators and all those involved in the process of teaching and learning are usually geared towards enhanced academic achievement of students. Academic achievement can be seen as the extent to which the students recorded success in their pursuit of learning. It is a direct manifestation of learning effectiveness and a valid indicator to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching and learning, as well as the overall development of students (Zhou and Siti, 2022).

Academic achievement of students sums up the overall performance in the course of study. It can be referred to as the extent at which the students recorded success in their pursuit of learning. Scholars agreed that students' academic achievement is a 'net result' of their cognitive and non-cognitive attributes which represents their overall achievement in academic records (Lee and Stankov, 2016). Active participation and interest in classroom learning contents contribute to enhanced academic achievement of the students. Academic achievement is a direct manifestation of learning effectiveness and a valid indicator to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching and

learning in higher education as well as the overall development of students (Zhou and Siti, 2022). Academic achievement of students in secondary schools is largely influenced by various factors and many researchers have made references to self-concept and academic interest. Onuoha and Odoh (2020) asserted that teachers are at the center of instructional delivery and the classroom is managed effectively under the guidance of a qualified teacher to facilitate learning. The teacher is the classroom manager, counselor and motivator. McIntyre, Santiago, Sutherland and Garbacz (2023) opined that students' academic interest, engagement and motivation are more likely to be productive through active participation in class discussions and activities. When teachers effectively engage the students in classroom learning experiences, students' interest in learning will be stimulated towards enhanced academic achievement. In anticipation of the need for a high level of academic achievement of students especially in public secondary schools, it is envisaged that the academic achievement of students could be enhanced through integration of quality teaching measures and students' academic interest.

Academic interest shows self-curiosity and zeal for learning and exploring academic ideas and subjects. Academic interest is the kind of interests that are integral to personal and situational interest to achieve educational goals (Onah and Anamezie, 2022). Students with

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higher levels of academic interest tend to achieve higher academically (Pérez-López and Ibarrondo-Dávila, 2020). This is to say that academic interest most times is intrinsic and reinforces the learner from within to learn. This can be influenced through engagements, motivations and encouragement. Academic interest was examined and highlighted into four components which includes academic emotion, academic value, academic knowledge and academic engagement (Luo, Dang and Xu, 2019). Academic interest fosters positive feelings accompanying the learning activities with excitement. Academic interest reflects personal perception of academic importance to the individual for stored knowledge in a specific domain. Students who have a high level of individual academic interest prefer to join in more learning activities (Mazer, 2013). Basically, students who do not have a high level of individual academic interest do not prefer to join in more learning activities. Thus, students' desire to learn can sustain and deepen academic interest for specific learning contents and experiences.

Academic interest plays an essential role in enhancing student motivation by being a powerful force that improves learning and performance (Simunović and Babarović, 2020). Academic interest is related to choices on subjects or academic activities fostered by intrinsic motivation. This can be driven by a genuine desire to learn rather than external rewards. Cents-Boonstra, Lichtwarck-Aschoff,

Denessen, Aelterman and Haerens (2021), affirmed that academic interest can be fueled by personal interest, motivating and encouraging students to engage deeply in learning processes. Academic interest often leads to greater engagement and improved performance, as interested students are more likely to participate actively and spend additional time studying (Koenka, 2020).

Academic interest portrays one's desire for learning activities, learning experiences and concepts. It enhances learning enthusiasm, relating to learning motivations and reflects feelings of joy and willingness to learn. Academic interest of students encompasses the involvement of both the cognitive and affective domain of learning as well as the psychomotor. Thus, every learner has the opportunity to excel in academics considering a personal interest in a preferred domain of learning. The researcher ponders if academic interest is considered and utilized as an integral part of instructional delivery to collaborate with self-concept in enhancing academic achievement of students in English Language in secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Teaching and learning English Language involves full concentration which necessitates a learner with passion, zeal and willingness to learn. Outstanding academic achievement calls for hard work and perseverance on both the English teachers and students. There is a crucial need for encouragement and motivation of the students by a skillful English Language teacher

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for a quality and successful instructional delivery. This will also help to maintain outstanding achievement and excellence in English Language at the secondary school level both in internal and external examinations.

English Language is among the core subjects whose credit pass remains compulsory in gaining admission into the University Education for most of the preferred courses of study. More so Nnewi Education Zone is becoming a famous enterprising business hub city, regularly explored by various non-indigenous entrepreneurs for commerce and industrialization, and English Language is perceived as a common means of communication for interactions. Hence students in the Nnewi Education Zone need to have a good command of the English Language. With earnest passion towards inculcating knowledge, English Language teachers in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone ought to seek effective approaches to engage the students on teaching and learning process for better understanding of learning contents. These purposes can be extensively achieved by encouraging the students to develop self-concept and embrace academic interest in which this study aimed to relatively correlate with academic achievement of students in English Language.

According to Zalmon and Wonu (2017), increased academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics are greatly needed to attain the Nigeria National Development Aspiration by the year 2030. Ojukwu (2017),

observed that public secondary schools still face significant challenges regarding students' academic achievement in English Language to meet up with the standard academic achievement level. The NECO Annual Report (2022), revealed that candidates who sat for the Year 2021 SSCE examination in Anambra State and recorded Credit Pass in Mathematics and English Language were 66.67%. This record shows moderate achievement scores. However, the annual record of (2023), revealed that candidates who sat for the SSCE examination and recorded credit pass in English Language were 47.05% which indicated a decrease and low achievement scores. The WASSCE Annual Report (2023), shows the general performance of candidates in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE); in Year 2022, out of 271,642 candidates who sat for the examination, a total of 86,926 (32%) candidates obtained credits in five subjects and above including English Language and Mathematics while in Year 2023, out of 265,819 candidates who sat for the West African Senior School Certificate Examination, only 88,252 (33.2%) scored five credits in Mathematics, English Language and any three other subjects which show only a slim difference.

These academic records call for concern to work on improved performances. Nwachukwu (2022), noted that one of the major challenges of teaching and learning for improved academic achievement is how to motivate and encourage the students to learn. More efforts ought to be made by the principals and teachers in Anambra State, especially Nnewi Education Zone towards encouraging, stimulating and motivating the interests of students to learn. The focus is aimed

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at increasing the academic achievement of the students. Students who are encouraged to believe in themselves and develop interest in learning will perform better in school and record increased academic performances. The need for greater academic achievement especially in English Language becomes essential in the public secondary schools in Nnewi education zone. This situation necessitates the study.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study examined academic interest as correlate of academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Research Question

The research questions below guided the study:

1. What are the academic interest scores of Public Secondary School Students in Nnewi Education Zone?
2. What are the English Language academic achievement scores of Public Secondary School Students in Nnewi Education Zone?
3. What is the correlation between the academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis below was formulated for the study and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant correlation between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Methods

Correlation research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 8,150 senior secondary school II (SS2) students in the 48 Public Secondary Schools in Nnewi

Education Zone. The zone is made up of 4 Local Government Areas; namely: Ekwusigo, Ihiala, Nnewi North and Nnewi South Local Government Areas. Multi-stage random sampling procedure was used to draw 10% of 8,150 students from the entire population, representing the sample size of the study. The instruments for data collection were Students' Academic Interest Questionnaire (SAIQ) and SS2 Students Achievements Scores (SAS) in English Language. The questionnaire was structured with each item assigned a four point scale of: Strongly Agree (SA); Agree (A); Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD), and corresponding values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The instrument was validated by experts in the field and considered fit for the study. The internal consistency of the items was obtained using Cronbach alpha which yielded an aggregate reliability coefficient of 0.81. The researcher administered the copies of the instrument directly to the respondents involving four research assistants. 782 copies of the instrument were administered to the respondents, successfully retrieved and used for data analysis. The percentage correlation among students' academic interest scores and English Language achievement scores were ascertained using the scores of SS2 students. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation coefficient (r) was used to answer the research questions and hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The coefficient (r) between 0.0 - 0.40 yielded a low positive relationship, between 0.41 - 0.60 yielded a moderate positive relationship, between 0.61 - 0.80 yielded a high positive relationship and between 0.81 - 1.00 yielded a very high substantial positive relationship. In testing the hypothesis the decision rules that

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when p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis were rejected, (there is a significant relationship). Otherwise, where the p-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was not rejected (there is no significant relationship). Data analysis was computed using the Statistical

Table 1: Range of scores on academic interest of public secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone.

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
24 - 44 Interest	496	63.4	Low Academic
45 - 71 Interest	286	36.6	High Academic

Table 1 shows that a total number of 496 students being 63.4% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 24 to 44 reported of having low academic interest while 286 students representing 36.6% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 45 to 71 reported of having

Table 2: Range of scores on academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone.

Range of Scores	N	%	Remarks
0 - 39	31	4.0	Poor Achievement
40 - 49	422	54.0	Fair Achievement
50 - 69	306	39.0	Good Achievement
70 - 100 Achievement	23	3.0	Very Good

Package for Social Sciences Version 23 (SPSS, 2023).

Results

Research Question One. What are the academic interest scores of public secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone?

high academic interest in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Research Question Two. What are the academic achievement scores of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone?

Table 2 shows that a total number of 31 students being 4.0% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 0 to 39, reported poor academic achievement in English Language. Also 422 students representing 54.0% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 40 to 49, reported fair academic achievement in English Language and 306 students representing 39.0% of the respondents with the scores ranging from 50 to 69, reported good academic achievement in English Language. Meanwhile, 23 students

representing 3.0% of the respondents with scores ranging from 70 to 100, reported very good academic achievement in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Research Question Three. What is the correlation between the academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone?

Table 3: Pearson (r) correlation on the relationship between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone

Source of Variation	N	r	Remarks
Academic Interest	782	.711	High Positive Relationship
Academic Achievement			

Results in Table 3 showed that Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) of 0.691 was obtained. The 0.704 correlation coefficient (r) is also between 0.61 and 0.80 showing a high positive relationship. This indicates that there is a high positive relationship existing between academic interest and academic achievement of students

in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Null Hypothesis one: There is no significant relationship between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Table 4: Test of significance of Pearson’s correlation between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Source of Variation	N	r	P-value	Remarks
Academic Interest	782	.711	0.000	*Significant
Academic Achievement				

Analysis in Table 4 showed that there is a significant relationship between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. The calculated r (0.711) had a P -value of 0.000 less than 0.05 level of significance level ($0.00 < 0.05$). The null hypothesis two, which states that there is no significant relationship between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study clearly indicated that the majority of the students in the zone experience low academic interest. It means that a greater number of the students do not have the self-curiosity and willingness for learning to explore the academic ideas and knowledge. This report implied that the low academic achievement of these students are largely influenced by their lack of zeal for learning due to low academic interest. This finding, agreed with Mappadang, Khusaini, Sinaga and

Elizabeth (2022), revealed that academic interest has a positive relationship with academic achievement of students. They pointed out that students with high academic interest possess bigger chances to record better academic achievement. Inversely, this implies that students with low academic interest, record lower academic achievement.

The findings also revealed that 36.6% of the students in the zone have high academic interest. Though this report showed a lesser number of students. However, there are still some students in Nnewi Education Zone who have the self-curiosity, enthusiasm and willingness for learning to explore academic ideas, acquiring skills and knowledge. This implies that these categories of students have intrinsic motivation stirred from the within, which reinforces them as learners to learn. This finding aligned with Onah and Anamezie (2022), who noted that academic interest has a high predictive value on academic achievement of public secondary schools students. When

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students develop interest in studying, their academic achievement will improve.

The report of this finding indicated that the majority of the students recorded fair performances resulting in low academic achievement in English Language. This report is in line with the NECO Annual Report (2022), which revealed that candidates who sat for the Year 2021 SSCE examination in Anambra State and recorded credit pass in Mathematics and English Language were 66.67%. However, this result was reported as a low achievement record. The findings also agreed with the WASSCE Annual Report (2023), which revealed that the general performance of candidates in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE); in the year 2022 & 2023 and obtained credit pass in Mathematics and English Language were 32.0% and 33.2% respectively. This also clearly indicated a low academic achievement score. Improved efforts are expected from the principals and teachers in Anambra State, especially Nnewi Education Zone towards motivating and stimulating interests of the students to learn. The focus will be aimed at increasing the academic achievement of the students in English Language.

Further findings of this study indicated that 3.0% of the students in the zone recorded very good achievement while 39.0% recorded fair achievement scores. Though the report revealed fair academic achievement, there could still be records of greater achievement scores of the students; if improved strategies and enhanced approaches are adopted in teaching and

learning of the English Language. However, it could still turn out otherwise if the strategies and measures taken to improve the students' academic achievement were unproductive. This finding concurred with Nwachukwu (2022), who noted that one of the major challenges of teaching and learning for improved academic achievement is how to motivate and encourage the students to learn. Ojukwu (2017), in the study observed that public secondary schools in Anambra State still face significant challenges regarding students' academic achievement in English Language. Obviously, most of the schools still struggle to meet up with the standard academic achievement level. The lesser percentage of the students representing 42.0% indicated that public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone still face challenges in learning the English Language. Therefore, the need for an improved teaching and learning process on the subject becomes crucial.

The findings also showed a high positive relationship existing between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. This result revealed that the willingness and curiosity of learners towards studies help the students in understanding the learning contents and experiences for increased academic achievement. This finding implies that academic interest also stimulates desires of the students for education and are facilitated by intrinsic motivations which helps them to do better in their studies. It means that students who possess high academic interests continually expand their learning skills and abilities and

embrace new knowledge. The expansion of the skills and knowledge give more insight to learning, and as such enhanced academic achievement. This finding aligned with Akuezuilo, Mbachu and Akunne (2022), who expressed that academic interests are characterized by such overwhelming and magnetic positive feelings to embrace knowledge and improved skills in the cognitive process for greater achievement. In the same vein, Onah and Anamezie (2022), observed that high academic engagement of students in learning contents promotes high academic achievement.

More findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between academic interest and academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary school students in Nnewi Education Zone. This means that academic interest is a source of motivation and strength to secondary school students as they face the uncertainty of the level of academic achievement. This result clearly indicates that the level of interest of a learner towards learning determines the level of commitment towards the studies. This is to say that students who have strong interest in academics will learn record high achievement scores while those who do not have interest in academics will record low achievement scores. Thus, increased interests yield increased performances. This is in line with Eze and Ejide (2025), which revealed that high academic interest among students can lead to an increase in academic achievement while low academic interest among students can lead

to academic failure, dropping out of school and the increase of negative emotions such as anxiety and depression. Also the study of Obi and Okoye (2023), affirmed a significant relationship between students' academic interest and academic achievement and concluded that students' academic interest has a high positive relationship with academic achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that academic interest is a correlate of academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone. That is to say that, Academic interest has a significant and high positive correlation with the academic achievement of students in English Language in public secondary schools in Nnewi Education Zone.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Anambra State government in collaboration with the principals in Nnewi Education Zone should organize seminars, workshops or conferences to enlighten the students on the need to develop academic interest towards learning of school subjects especially the English Language.
2. The State Post Primary School Service Commission should also encourage the principals and teachers to educate the students on the need to develop interest in academics to enable them have a completion of academic cycle, in their educational programmes.

References

- Akuezuilo, J., Mbachu, C. U., and Akunne, L. I. (2022). Academic Interest and Self-Esteem As Correlates of Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in English Language in Nigeria. *Advances in Research*, 23 (3), 13-22.
- Cents-Boonstra, M., Lichtwarck-Aschoff, A., Denessen, E., Aelterman, N., and Haerens, L. (2021). Fostering student engagement with motivating teaching: An observation study of teacher and student behaviours. *Research Papers in Education*, 36(6), 754-779.
- Eze, C.U and Ejide, B. (2025). Academic interest as correlate of academic engagement among undergraduate students in public universities in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences and Humanities Research* 13(4), 274-280.
- Koenka, A. C. (2020). Academic motivation theories revisited: An interactive dialog between motivation scholars on recent contributions, underexplored issues, and future directions. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101831.
- Lee, J., and Stankov, L. (2016). *Non-cognitive psychological processes and academic achievement*. London: UK: Routledge.
- Luo, Z., Dang, Y. and Xu, W. (2019). Academic Interest Scale for Adolescents: Development, Validation, and Measurement Invariance with Chinese Students. *Front. Psychol.* 10:2301. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.02301
- Mappadang, A., Khusaini, K., Sinaga, M. and Elizabeth, E. (2022) Academic interest determines the academic performance of undergraduate accounting students: Multinomial logit evidence. *Cogent Business and Management Journal*, 9(1), 68-72.
- Mazer, J. P. (2013). Associations among teacher communication behaviors, student interest, and engagement: a validity test. *Communication Education*. 62(1), 86–96. doi: 10.1080/03634523.2012.731513
- McIntyre, L. L., Santiago, R. T., Sutherland, M., and Garbacz, S. A. (2023). Parenting stress and autistic children's emotional problems relating to family–school partnerships and parent mental health. *School Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000531>
- National Examinations Council Annual Report, (2022). NECO; *Federal Republic of Nigeria*.
- Nwachukwu, I. (2022). Academic interest and school environment as correlates of academic performance of students in public secondary schools in Okigwe Zone, Imo State. *International Journal of Education and Management Sciences*, 4(1), 226-238.

- Obi, J.S.C. and Okoye, U.M. (2023). Academic interest as correlate of academic achievement of undergraduates in public Universities in Anambra State. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies*. 16 (2), 148 -159.
- Ojukwu, M. O. (2017). Effect of insecurity of school environment on the academic performance of secondary school students in Imo State. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 5(1), 20-28.
- Onah, K.T. and Anamezie, R. C. (2022).The study investigated academic interest as a predictor of academic achievement of secondary school Physics. *AJSTME*, 8(4), 320-326.
- Onuoha, J. and Odo, S. (2020). Problems of teacher's education and its effects in the realization of the objectives of universal basic education in South East, Nigeria. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2), 71-79.
- Pérez-López, M. C. and Ibarrondo-Dávila, M. P. (2020). Key variables for academic performance in university accounting studies. A mediation model. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 57(3), 374-385.
- Šimunović, M., and Babarović, T. (2020). The role of parents' beliefs in students' motivation, achievement, and choices in the STEM domain: a review and directions for future research. *Social Psychology of Education*, 23(3), 701-719.
- West African Secondary School Certificate Examinations Annual Report, (2022). WASSCE; Federal Republic of Nigeria.
- Zalmon, I. G. and Wonu, N. (2017). Comparative analysis of student Mathematics achievement in West African Senior Secondary Certificate Examination in Nigeria. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Science*, 5(1), 24-37.
- Zhou, Z. and Siti, M. M. (2022). A literature review on the academic achievement of college students. *Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 20 (1), 289-295.